

**ACCEPTABILITY OF INCLUSION AMONG THE GENERAL TEACHERS
AT ELEMENTARY SCHOOL LEVEL**

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Abstract

It is primary duty of every nation to impart primary education to every child without any discrimination. In India, inclusive education is implemented all over in neighbourhood schools for the education of children with special needs under RTE, act. In this paper the central purpose of the study was to know the level of acceptability of general teachers towards the inclusion, to explore the opinion of different school teachers about the inclusion of visually impaired children and also making them aware of the inclusion of visually impaired children. The research was descriptive in its nature and 40 teachers were randomly selected for the collection of data. A close ended questionnaire was used for the data collection in which three point type scales was used to get the responses of the general teachers. Analysis of the result was done by calculating frequencies and percentages of responses. The majority of the general teachers had accepted the inclusion in the regular schools.

Key words: *Inclusion, Visually Impaired, General Teachers, Acceptability*

Background and Literature Review

The inclusive education is now major priority for Government of India because every child has right of education. The concept of inclusive education refers to including children with disabilities in the regular classes as full time in the nearest schools (Veiga,1997), the education can be provided to students by using adapted curriculum and instructional devices available for the children (Haider, 2008).

Recently, there has been a significant movement of including children with special needs into general education classrooms after the implementation of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan and RTE, act. This is due to many international declarations including Universal Declaration on Human Rights,1948(Article,26),the Convention on the Rights of the Child(1989), Jomtien World Conference on Education for All(1990),The Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education,

The Dakar Framework for Education of All(2000),and most recently the United Nation Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006).

In the schools, the teachers are perceived to be main person in the implementation of inclusive education. Many research studies indicated that teachers are the key to the success of inclusionary programs, inclusive education can only be successful if teachers are part of this process.

It is significant to study the acceptance of school teachers toward the inclusion into regular settings because their perceptions influence their acceptance of the children with visual impairment in the inclusive settings.

Objectives

1. To find out the acceptance of inclusion among the general teachers towards the education of children with visual impairment at elementary school level.
2. To acquire the suggestions of the general teachers for the successful implementation the inclusion.

Methodology

It was a descriptive type of research. The population of the study consisted of teachers working in the regular schools of kurukshetra district of Haryana state. The sample of study included 40 general teachers of government schools between 20- 56 years of elementary school level . The respondents were selected from 08 schools using simple random sampling technique. From each school 05 teachers were selected using balloting technique.

A structured questionnaire consisted of 18 items on three point scale (Yes, No, to some extent) was used to obtain the information/ data from the general teachers regarding the inclusion of children with visual impairment. The researcher personally interacted with all teachers for collection of data and suggestions.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 20. Frequency distribution of teachers' responses were calculated which are being presented in tabular form.

Table -1

Frequency distribution of teachers' responses

Sr. No	Statements	Acceptable	Acceptable to some extent	Not acceptable
1	Are you in favour of inclusion in regular school?	65	10	25
2	Inclusion is a better educational system for	54	08	38

	children with vision problems.			
3	It is a right of visually impaired children to receive education in a regular school	100	00	00
4	Are you thinking visually impaired children can get appropriate education in special schools?	80	20	00
5	The learning skills of visually impaired children are improved in regular school.	35	50	15
6	Inclusion is absolutely right based approach to the educational needs of visually impaired children	67	00	33
7	Are you thinking visually impaired children are able to have friendly relations with all children?	100	00	00
8	The attitude of staff working in school would be positive with visually impaired	100	00	00
9	Inclusion of visually impaired children in school also makes them useful citizens of the society.	90	10	00
10	Social skills of visually impaired children will be increased by studying in regular school.	95	05	00
11	Teachers in regular schools need special training for teaching visually impaired children.	100	00	00
12	The teachers will face no problems in the inclusion of visually impaired children	32	45	23
13	Visually impaired children may face difficulties in educational matters due to inattention of teachers.	15	20	65
14	The low vision lab/resource room is necessary for the inclusion of visually impaired children in regular schools.	100	00	00
15	Getting education in ordinary schools will have better effect on the psychological well being of visually impaired children.	82	18	00
16	Getting education in ordinary school will have better effect on the social development of	100	00	00

	visually impaired children.			
17	Visually impaired children will learn independent living skills through receiving education with sighted children.	69	12	19
18	Inclusion will play positive role in the personality development of visually impaired children.	100	00	00

Main Findings

Table-1 shows that majority of the school teachers (65%) were in full favour of inclusion whereas 10% teachers responded that it was acceptable to some extent.

All the teachers accepted that the inclusion is the right of the students with disabilities; a percentage like (35%) of teachers had opinion that inclusion had improved their social skills of the students with visual impairment.

Cent percent (100%) of the teachers accepted that they need training for the inclusion of students with visual impairment in regular schools.

All the teachers accepted that the a resource room and adapted labs in the schools will helpful in proper inclusion of the students. Moreover (69%) teachers also reported that inclusion is the appropriate solution for the development of social skills of students with visual impairment to some extent.

Cent percent (100%) of the teachers accepted that inclusion play a positive role in personality development of students .

Findings of some studies also indicated that academically successful students tend to attribute their successes and failures to their own efforts or actions. They persevere on difficult tasks, delay gratification, and are actively involved in the learning situation (Roy, 2000). Students with blindness and visual impairments often attribute their successes and failures to factors outside their control. They attribute success to their ability, effort, persistence, and discipline, and they point to external factors as contributors to their lack of academic success, such as difficulty in accessing information and the negative attitudes of faculty and administrators (Roy, 2000). Students with blindness and visual impairments were academically successful in college because of institutional support and the positive attitude of faculty and peers (Fichten, 2009; Roy, 2000). Weiner (2006) postulates that students attribute their success in college to internal factors, including ability, effort, mood, maturity, and health, and external factors,

including the teacher, task difficulty, family support. As Mukhopadhyay (2002) also indicated that assessing learning style of each child, duplicating, modifying without changing concept, substituting, giving similar experience and omitting, when unavoidable, are some strategies that teachers in the classroom can adopt

Educational Implications

The study will be helpful for the teachers on the curriculum adaptation, use of latest pedagogies and instructional strategies for teaching students with visual impairment in inclusive classrooms. It is also give depth of knowledge / information related to inclusive classroom management in the inclusion. It is a positive effort to enlighten the people about the philosophy of inclusion and its importance.

Conclusion

On the basis of the findings of the study it can be concluded that majority of the teachers accepted the inclusion of the children with visual impairment in their schools, however, they also indicate that students with visual impairment need much more adaptation in schools activities. For this teachers will have to concern on the special needs of the visual impaired students not only in the school but also in the classrooms.

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